

BBSRC Bioscience for an Integrated Understanding of Health Non-Animal Technologies scoping meeting

Tom N McNeilly, Moredun Research Institute

A scoping meeting was held on 19th September to discuss the current status of Non-Animal Technologies (NAT) and future investment strategies for BBSRC and NC3Rs. Prof. Tom McNeilly (Moredun Research Institute) participated in this workshop to represent NAT in veterinary research.

Initial discussions included UK Government strategy on alternatives to animals in research, including the wider view to reduce the reliance on animals for regulatory testing and research and how this links to BBSRC's future research strategy.

Expert advice was provided on the future focus areas for BBSRC in NAT, identifying priority areas for scoping activities and key stakeholders. Models for funding of NAT in the veterinary research and bioscience sectors was discussed.

This outcomes of this scoping meeting are being used to develop BBSRCs policy on NAT, and develop strategic funding models to support the development and adoption of NAT in the Bioscience and veterinary sectors.